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FOSTERING STEM-ORIENTED TEACHING COMPETENCY FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS TO MEET THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE GENERAL EDUCATION PROGRAM 2018 IN VIETNAM

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Abstract

In the article, the author has referred to the requirements of the general education program 2018 for the secondary school teachers' STEM-oriented teaching competency and the fostering of this competency for them.

Keywords: secondary school, teachers, STEM, general education program, fostering, competency.

1. Introduction

The introduction of the general education program 2018 is an important milestone for the educational reform process in Vietnam. This educational program aims to help students master general knowledge, know how to effectively apply the learned knowledge and skills in life, know how to self-study lifelong, and develop their qualities as well as their competencies. Therefore, implementing the form of STEM-oriented teaching is the national policy for all educational levels. STEM-oriented education equips learners with the necessary knowledge and skills related to the fields of science (S), technology (T), engineering (E), and mathematics (M). These contents of knowledge and skills are taught integratedly, supplementing one another to help students understand the principles and be able to apply them to create products to serve in daily life [1].

The academic year 2021-2022 is the first year that the general education program 2018 is implemented at the secondary level. For the effective implementation of this program, it is necessary to prepare in many aspects such as facilities, teaching equipment and human resources etc. Therefore, fostering competencies for teachers including STEM-oriented teaching capacity, to meet the general education program 2018, is of particular concern.

In this article, we have referred to the requirements of the general education program 2018 for the secondary school teachers' STEM-oriented teaching competency and the fostering of this competency for them.

2. Contents

2.1. Requirements of the general education program 2018 for the secondary school teachers' STEM-oriented teaching competency in Vietnam

In the general education program 2018, STEM education is understood as «an educational model based on an interdisciplinary approach, helping students apply knowledge of science, technology, engineering and mathematics to solve practical problems in the particular contexts» [1]. Thus, STEM education is both meant to promote education in the fields of science, technology, engineering and mathematics, while demonstrating an interdisciplinary approach to help with developing learners' competencies and qualities.

STEM education is an idea-based curriculum that equips learners with knowledge and skills related to science, technology, engineering, and mathematics – in an interdisciplinary approach, and learners can apply their practices to solve problems in life. Instead of teaching the four subjects as separate and discrete ones, STEM combines them into a cohesive learning model

based on real-world applications. The knowledge and skills in the STEM education program must be integrated and complement one another, helping students not only understand basic knowledge but also be able to apply it to practice and create products in daily life. In which, as for science skills, students are equipped with knowledge of concepts, principles, laws and theoretical foundations of science education. In the process of educational development, the term STEM has been added with other elements depending on the goals and perspectives of the researcher. Currently, there are many variants relating the term STEM, such as: STEAM (added Arts to STEM), STREAM (added Robotics science to STEAM) etc. However, all are on the basis of STEM, and we all agree on the way it is called as STEM education. The most important goal is that, through science education, students are able to use and relate that knowledge to practice, and at the same time have an applied mindset to practice in order to solve real-world problems. As for technology skills, students are able to use, manage, understand and access technology, from very simple objects such as a pen and a fan to complex systems such as the Internet and computers. In terms of technical skills, students are equipped with the skills to produce an object of a product and understand the process to make it. This requires students to be able to synthesize and combine to know how to balance relevant elements (such as physics, arts, technology, and chemistry) in order to get the best solution in designing and building the process. In addition, students are required to be able to recognize the needs and reactions from the society in technology-related issues. Finally, math skill is the ability to recognize and grasp the role of mathematics in all aspects existing in life. Therefore, students are trained to have the math skills in order to perform their ideas correctly and to have the ability to apply mathematical theories and skills to daily life.

* STEM education activities can be organized through the following forms:

- STEM education through experiential activities and scientific research: In STEM experiential activities, students can explore experiments and apply scientific and technological applications in real life. In scientific research activities, STEM education is associated with science and technology creation contests and entrepreneurship for students from many different topics.

- STEM education through teaching STEM subjects: In subjects, especially in natural sciences, there are different topics associated with STEM education. STEM topics can be designed to teach in different ways, such as: STEM topics designed to be taught in a single subject, STEM topics are designed for teaching in a variety of subjects, and STEM topics for combined subjects. However, in order to design a STEM education model, it is necessary to follow a certain process to achieve the educational goals. It is essential to implement the form of STEM teaching conforming to the process of certain steps to achieve educational goals as follows: Step 1 - Identifying the practical problems to be solved, step 2 - Forming hypotheses oriented to solve practical problems, step 3-

Exploring and mobilizing knowledge regarding practical problems, step 4- Developing plans and solutions to solve practical problems, step 5- Organizing to solve problems, and step 6 - Summarizing, evaluating, and experience learning.

From the above-stated goals, requirements, and characteristics, for effective STEM-oriented teaching, teachers need to have a deep understanding of STEM education, have the ability to use methods and organizational forms of STEM education, implement STEM-oriented education teaching activities as stated in the correct process, test and evaluate the results of this teaching activity.

2.2. Contents of fostering STEM - oriented teaching competency for teachers in secondary schools

To develop STEM-oriented teaching competency for secondary school teachers, it is indispensable to foster them with the following contents:

** Basic theoretical issues of STEM education*

First of all, it is vital to equip teachers with basic understanding of STEM education such as: STEM concepts, STEM education concept, forms and methods of STEM education, teaching process of STEM oriented education; The role and meaning of STEM education etc.

** Competency to select and develop STEM topics:*

Forming in teachers the skills to identify and design STEM topics that are organized and integrated in a regular or extra-curricular period/lesson according to the following criteria: 1. Developing STEM topics that focus on real-world problems, 2. Structuring STEM topics according to the engineering design process, 3. STEM-themed teaching methods that bring students into the activities of exploring and discovering, action and orientation, experience and products, 4. The forms of organizing STEM topics that attract students to the constructivist group activities, 5. Contents of STEM topics to be applied in reality must be mainly from science, math and technology that students have been learning, 6. The progression of STEM topics should take into account multiple correct answers and treat failure as a necessary part of learning.

* *Competency to make teaching plans for STEM-oriented lessons*, including: planning process and building STEM lessons, identifying and coordinating elements to perform STEM lessons, building a system of activities for students etc.

* *Competency to organize the teaching STEM – oriented education activity*, including: skills to orient topics and organize activities for students, skills to guide, encourage and control activities for students, skills to use teaching aids for STEM lessons.

* *Competency to evaluate students' STEM-oriented learning activities*. For this capacity, it is necessary to foster teachers with the following contents: Developing criteria for evaluating STEM lessons, steps to analyze students' learning activities, collecting records and giving evaluation results.

2.3. Forms of fostering STEM – oriented teaching competency for teachers in secondary schools

Some basic forms of fostering STEM-oriented

teaching competency for teachers in secondary schools are as follows:

Contests: Contest format is a way to organize contests and competitions with a large gathering of teachers in order to achieve the goal of fostering STEM education capacity for teachers. Topics that can be used for these contests include: Contests to learn about modern teaching methods and techniques, organizing training sessions on STEM education topics, essay writing contests on experiencing the innovation of teaching methods according to STEM-oriented education in secondary schools etc.

Workshops: This is the form of teachers' discussion on theoretical and practical issues of STEM education. The organizers need to clearly define the objectives, contents, forms, means, time, place and budget, then have a proper announcement on the workshops so as to mobilize participants, especially scientists and experts on the subjects of STEM education.

Training: Training is a process to help with forming in teachers the ability to organize effective STEM education activities. Various forms of teacher training can be used, depending on the training objectives, for example: Standardized training or/and regular training periodically, fostering through training courses as planned by the Departments of Education and Training, fostering through group activities and professional groups at the school, fostering through teachers' self-study (through curriculum, materials on STEM education that are provided).

In addition, other forms of fostering can be used such as: training through conferences, seminars, study tours, etc.

2.4. Methods of fostering STEM-oriented teaching competency for teachers in secondary schools

Some of the important methods that can be used in fostering STEM-oriented teaching competencies for secondary school teachers are stated as follows:

Presentation: This is the method by which the presenter uses his own words to explain an issue, or present a document on STEM education. The presentation method is combined with illustrations and practice.

Discussion: This is a method that is effectively applied in fostering teachers generally and fostering teaching competency in STEM-oriented education particularly. Using this method, the presenter divides

participants into small groups, then assigns each group with a topic to discuss STEM-oriented teaching. The members in each group exchange and share ideas with one another to reach an agreement on the common results of the group.

Case-solving method: The presenter provides situations arose in STEM-oriented teaching so that the participants can analyze, evaluate and solve problems in the situations.

The fostering methods need to be consistent with the contents and suitable with the forms of fostering to stimulate learners' active learning and ensure the effectiveness of training activities. Additionally, it is necessary to ensure the conditions for fostering teaching competency in STEM-oriented education for teachers in secondary schools in terms of human resources who participate in the training as well as in terms of facilities for training activities (appropriate rooms for learning, conferences and seminars; guaranteed technical equipment; sufficient training materials; sample classrooms on STEM education)

3. Conclusion

Teaching competency in STEM - oriented education is an important component competency that general teachers in Vietnam need to have in order to meet the requirements of the general education program 2018. Therefore, fostering to improving this teaching competency for teachers is inevitable. There should be consistency between the contents, methods, and forms of fostering, and ensure the necessary conditions for the forces who participate in the training and for facilities to serve the fostering in order for the training activities to be most effective.

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